

***In-Vitro* Release Profiles of a Combination of Doxorubicin and Methotrexate from Hydroxyapatite-Sodium Alginate Nanocomposite**

*Onoyima C.C¹. and Aroh A.O¹.

¹Department of Chemistry, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Nigeria

Abstract: Co-delivery of two or more anticancer drugs enhances efficiency and combat multidrug resistance (MDR). In this study, simultaneous loading of two anticancer drugs – Doxorubicin (DOX) and Methotrexate (MTX) into hydroxyapatite-sodium alginate (HASA) nanocomposite was carried out in aqueous media following adsorption methods, while in-vitro drug release was carried out in synthetic body fluid (SBF) medium at 37°C and pH 7.4 under sterile conditions. The encapsulation efficiency of DOX at DOX: MTX ratios of 16:1, 4:1, 1:1, 1:4, and 1:16 are 86.50%, 88.42%, 90.00%, 89.15%, and 87.90% respectively. However, for MTX There was high encapsulation efficiency (91.80%) at a low concentration of MTX (0.125 mg/cm³), which decreased to 37.54% at a high concentration (2 mg/cm³). The release profiles for all the combination ratios showed high burst release for MTX with total release time not exceeding five hours. However, for DOX the drug release had an initial burst release and then sustained for the thirty-three hours of the study. The observed time-differential release of each drug from the dual drug-encapsulated carrier is highly important if a synergistic effect can be obtained in to combat multi-drug resistance (MDR).

Keywords: Combination therapy, Doxorubicin, Methotrexate, drug resistance, cancer

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1.0. Introduction

Some of the major issues in the treatment of cancer are multidrug resistance (MDR), narrow therapeutic window, and undesired side effects of available anticancer drugs are the limitations of anticancer drugs (Gurunathan *et al.*, 2018). Cancer cells often develop multiple resistances to different functionally unrelated drugs. This is known as multi-drug resistance. Cancer multi-drug resistance is defined as the cross-resistance or insensitivity of cancer cells to the cytostatic or cytotoxic actions of various anticancer drugs, which are structurally or functionally unrelated and have different molecular targets (Gottesman, 2002).

The two mechanisms involved in cancer drug resistance are classified as cellular and non-cellular mechanisms. The non-cellular mechanism can occur in one or more of the following ways: reduced access of the drug to tumour cells due to the poorly vascularised nature of tumour regions; ionization of basic drugs in the acidic environment of the tumour which prevents their diffusion across the cellular membrane (the pH around tumour tissues in the body is more acidic (~5.5 – 6.5), relative to physiological pH which is 7.4 (Magadala *et al.*,

2008); reduced extravasations of drug molecules due to high vascular pressure and low microvascular pressure of the tumour site (Kakde *et al.*, 2011).

The cellular mechanism involves a plasma membrane protein known as p-glycoprotein (P-gp). P-gp which is over-expressed in tumour tissues is capable of binding to the drug molecules, forming trans-membrane channels, and pumping the drug molecules out of the cell using the energy of the ATP hydrolysis (Kakde *et al.*, 2011). In addition, after repeated treatments, surviving cancer cells can undergo some genetic mutation leading to the acquisition of resistance to the drug.

The most common mechanism of multi-drug resistance is the over-expression of the drug efflux pump (P-gp) (Hu & Zhang, 2009). Krishna and Mayer (2000), have proposed co-administration of P-gp inhibitor with nanoparticles encapsulated anticancer drugs as a way of preventing P-gp mediated multi-drug resistance. Another approach is the use of combination therapy. Combination chemotherapy is the administration of multiple agents that have different mechanisms of action.

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The multiple agents used must work synergistically (Kogashiwa & Kohno, 2013). Combination therapy with anticancer drugs has been shown to generally induce synergistic drug actions and deter the onset of drug resistance. In addition to this, combination therapy also provides synergistically enhanced therapeutic outcomes without added toxicity, overcomes tumour heterogeneity or 'preferable' drug responsiveness of various cells within the same cancer type, and enhanced efficacy (Farooq *et al.*, 2018; Gurunathan *et al.*, 2018; Kumar *et al.*, 2023). The compounds having the ability to reverse resistance against anticancer drugs are called MDR inhibitors, chemosensitizers, or MDR modulators (Kellen, 2003).

Hydroxyapatite/polymer composites have attracted much attention since such composites lead to improved properties (Khaled *et al.*, 2014) as a result of improvement in the surface functionality of the apatite (Venkatesan *et al.*, 2011). Such improvement has led to wide applications and potential applications of hydroxyapatite polymer composites in many areas such as in drug delivery systems (Raj *et al.*, 2013; Prasanna & Venkatasubbu, 2018; Sukhodud *et al.*, 2018; Reza *et al.*, 2019; Albahy *et al.*, 2020), cell culture and tissue engineering (Zheng *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2020; Monte *et al.*, 2023), dental technology (Lee *et al.*, 2016; Lu *et al.*, 2022), antimicrobials (Castro-Mayorga *et al.*, 2016; Benedini *et al.*, 2020), pollution remediation (Gardi *et al.*, 2015; Ragab *et al.*, 2019; Al-Bazedi & Abdel-Fatah, 2020), and so on.

This research aims to investigate the loading efficiencies of Doxorubicin and Methotrexate into hydroxyapatite-sodium alginate nanocomposite and its in-vitro release profiles, as a preliminary study for the possibility of use as combination therapy.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1. Drug loading

Studies have shown that radiometric dosing (controlling drug ratios following systemic administration) of anticancer drug combinations can profoundly influence therapeutic outcomes (Mayer *et al.*, 2006). In this study, different drug combination ratios were used to evaluate the suitability of the nanocomposites for combination therapy. The drugs were mixed in a

combination ratio (DOX: MTX) of 16:1, 4:1, 1:1, 1:4, and 1:16. The drugs were loaded simultaneously following the adsorption method described earlier (Onoyima *et al.*, 2017).

A series of standards were prepared for both drugs and the absorbance was taken at both wavelengths of maximum absorbance for DOX (290 nm) and MTX (419 nm). Calibration graphs were plotted for the two drugs at both wavelengths. This is because absorbance is additive. Drug loading and release were evaluated by taking the absorbance of the supernatant at both wavelengths and solving simultaneously to obtain the concentrations of the two drugs in the solution.

2.2. In-vitro drug release study

The *in vitro* drug release study was carried out following a method reported by Sivakumar and Rao, (2002). To determine the drug release profile, 100 mg of the drug-loaded nanocomposites were introduced into a screw-capped glass bottle containing 50 cm³ of synthetic body fluid (SBF) medium at 37°C and pH 7.4 under sterile conditions. Aliquots of 5 cm³ samples were withdrawn by a pipette at regular intervals and replaced immediately with 5 cm³ of fresh SBF medium (this was accounted for when calculating the amount released). Drug concentrations in the collected samples were measured using UV-VIS Spectrophotometer.

The quantity of the drug released at any time Q_t was calculated using the equation:

$$Q_t = C_t V_T + v \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} C_{ti} \quad (1)$$

where Q_t is the quantity of drug (mg) released at the time point t ; C_t is the concentration (mg/cm³) at time t , V_T is the total volume (cm³) of the release medium, v is the volume (cm³) of the sample, $\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} C_{ti}$ is the summation of C from $i = 1$ to $n-1$, and i is the n th sample. The second part of the right-hand side of the equation, $v \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} C_{ti}$ is the volume correction, used to account for the amount of the drug discarded at every sampling point.

While the percent cumulative release (%Cr_t) at any time point t is:

$$\%Cr_t = \frac{Q_t}{Q_T} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

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Where %Cr_t is the percent cumulative release at time t (h), and Q_T is the quantity of the drug

MTX drug content is thought to be due to undissolved drugs in the solution. MTX is not very soluble in aqueous solution. A similar observation was reported by Shi *et al.*, (2014) and Sharma *et al.*, (2016), which was attributed to a combination of drug-polymer interactions and drug solubility.

3.0. Results and Discussion

3.1. Drug loading

The quest for nanoparticle-assisted combination therapy is driven by its ability to unify the pharmacokinetics of different drugs by simultaneously delivering multiple drugs; this in turn offers synergistic therapeutic effect between the drugs and suppresses drug resistance.

The results of DOX and MTX encapsulation efficiency at different combination ratios are presented in Figure 1. The study was conducted at DOX: MTX combination ratio of 16:1, 4:1, 1:1, 1:4, and 1:16. The encapsulation efficiency of DOX at DOX: MTX ratio of 16:1, 4:1, 1:1, 1:4 and 1:16 are 86.50%, 88.42%, 90.00%, 89.15% and 87.90% respectively (Figure 1). This indicates that the encapsulation efficiency of DOX was high irrespective of the relative concentration of DOX in the mixture. In other words, DOX encapsulation efficiency did not depend on loading concentration within the concentration range studied (2 mg/cm³ – 0.125 mg/cm³). However, for MTX the encapsulation efficiency decreased as the concentration of MTX increased. There was high encapsulation efficiency (91.80%) at a low concentration of MTX (0.125 mg/cm³), which decreased to 37.54% at a high concentration (2 mg/cm³). Electrostatic interaction, intercalation, hydrogen bonding, and physical adsorption might be involved in the loading of MTX and DOX into the nanocomposites. FTIR studies have indicated chemical interaction between DOX and HASA from the sodium alginate part of the nanocomposite, whereas no evidence of such interaction was observed between MTX and the nanocomposite (Onoyima *et al.*, 2017; Onoyima *et al.*, 2016). The higher encapsulation efficiency of DOX was attributed to this chemical interaction between the drug and the nanocomposite. A previous study has also reported a significant influence of the interaction between the drug and carrier on the encapsulation efficiency (Dhakar *et al.*, 2010). The observed significant decrease in encapsulation efficiency with an increase in

3.2. In-vitro drug release study

The release profiles for all the combination ratios are shown in Figures 2-6. MTX showed high burst release with a total release time not exceeding five hours. High burst release of MTX was similar to the observation by Mahkam *et al.*, (2021) and Huang & Brazel, (2001), which was explained based on the surface adsorption of the drug to the nanocomposite. A further kinetic study was not carried out on MTX because of the short release time.

However, for DOX the drug release had an initial burst release and then sustained for the thirty-three hours of the study. The DOX release was decreased due to drug-nanocomposite interaction and higher entrapment of the drug. The cumulative DOX release at 33h was approximately 100 mg for all the combinations. DOX release followed first order release rate while the release mechanism from Korsmeyer-Peppas exponent n is by Fickian diffusion. Drug release from a system with n > 0.45 is due to diffusion through a matrix and water-filled pores, where molecular diffusion of the drug due to chemical potential gradient is the rate-limiting step (Shende & Maratha 2015)

The co-release of the two drugs showed that there was a time-differential release between DOX and MTX from HASA. The differential release of the drugs was thought to be due to the difference between the physicochemical states of each drug in the nanocomposite. When sequential actions of two drugs are essential to cause a synergistic effect of the drugs, the time-differential release of each drug from the dual drug-encapsulated carrier is highly important. Combination therapy enhances transport and penetration of drugs into the deep tissue of solid tumours (Hu *et al.*, 2010). To achieve this enhanced transport and penetration, the high burst release of MTX can be beneficial. The first released drugs can induce partial cancer apoptosis and expand the interstitial space of the

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solid tumour, thus the nanoparticles can diffuse into the deep tumour tissue and continue to release the second drug.

Figure 1: Loading efficiencies of drugs combined at different ratios (DOX: MTX)

Figure 3: Release profiles of DOX and MTX at a combination ratio of 4: 1 (DOX: MTX)

Figure 2: Release profiles of DOX and MTX at a combination ratio of 16: 1 (DOX: MTX)

Figure 4: Release profiles of DOX and MTX at a combination ratio of 1: 1 (DOX: MTX)

Figure 5: Release profiles of DOX and MTX at a combination ratio of 1: 4 (DOX: MTX)

Figure 6: Release profiles of DOX and MTX at a combination ratio of 1: 16 (DOX: MTX)

Although combination therapy can create therapeutic benefits when the agents work synergistically or additively, there can also be drug interactions leading to a build-up of toxicity (Riechelmann *et al.*, 2007). The increased complexity of the formulation is another setback to this promising field (Gurunathan *et al.*, 2018). Hence, the drug interactions of the combined agents at each ratiometric dose must be carefully studied for maximum therapeutic benefits.

4.0. Conclusion

The drug combination study showed that the release profiles for all the combination ratios have high burst release for MTX with total release time not exceeding five hours. However, for DOX the drug release was sustained

throughout the thirty-three hours of the study. There should be further investigation into the drug combination study using other methods of drug loading, and other different drug combination ratios, to establish the effect and dose level for synergism.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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